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“REDISCOVERING THE MEMORIAL TOWN OF SOUTHERN LEYTE: THE MUNICIPALITY OF PADRE BURGOS”

Padre Burgos started its journey as a humble barrio of the town of Malitbog in the mid-18th century. Early Burgosanons were residing in “Pueblo Viejo” (old town), now called Lungsodaan, a present-day barangay of the Municipality of Padre Burgos. Pueblo Viejo is a small coastal area where the famous Moro Watchtower is situated, and was once a part of the town of Malitbog. The small coastal area was the place where the early Burgosanons dreamed of a better and prosperous community. As the population increased due to the influx of people from other places and neighboring areas, and the limited habitation in Pueblo Viejo, the elders and leaders of the early Burgosanons decided to relocate their poblacion to “Matnog”, a sitio of Pueblo Viejo which was much wider and bigger in area than the old poblacion. Matnog is below sea level and characterized by saltwater marshes and swamps, which explains why the early Burgosanon is so dependent on marine life resources for their daily survival. At that time, the clans of Gilles, Naron, Leyson, Telen, and Palermo were the notable early Burgosanon families in Matnog. These families and other members of the community worked hard and left no stone unturned in expanding and developing the barrio.

During the incumbency of barrio Capitan Venancio Leyson, the sitio name was changed from Matnog to “Tamolayag”, a name coined from the local phrase “Tana Molayag” (Let’s sail). The phrase is not just an ordinary call to fishing but a resounding warning against the approaching brutish Moro pirates at that time. These Moro pirates swept and raided the coastal barrios and towns of the Sogod Bay area and brought havoc and untold miseries upon its inhabitants. Because of this rampant Moro piracy, Capitan Venancio spearheaded the construction of the Moro Watchtower in the old poblacion of Pueblo Viejo to provide a lookout on approaching Moro pirates. During Moro raids, bamboo gongs were sounded, and the people, upon hearing the gongs, shouted, “Tana Molayag”. The people immediately jumped into their sailboats and, without fear, sailed toward Panaon Island, where they sought refuge in the dense jungles of the island. But Capitan Venancio and other men in the barrio fought face-to-face against the marauders. Capitan Venancio’s leadership and valor acts during the Spanish campaign against Moro piracy caught the attention of the Spanish authorities, and the Spanish Comandante Politico-Militar of Leyte honored him with a pyramid-shaped monument and changed his family name from Leyson to Piramide, a name that symbolizes bravery and solidity of purpose as solid as a pyramid-like statue.

Barrio Tamolayag, like other places in the Philippines, did not escape the reign of terror and discrimination of the Spanish government. The Sta. Sofia Canal, aside from being a pride of the barrio, constructed through forced labor on a rotating schedule, was an example of the Spanish abuses and discrimination against the people of barrio Tamolayag and its neighboring places. The canal signified wealth, security, and efficiency

inasmuch as trade and commerce are concerned. Vessels and bancas traveling in and out of Sogod Bay could securely navigate this canal rather than circumnavigating Tangkaan point, where the currents are quite powerful and pose risks for navigators. Thus, saving time, money, and energy. The canal also offered a safe docking area for bancas and other small boats during typhoons and adverse weather conditions. Despite its benefits, it cannot hide the injustices that the early Burgosanons suffered. Though the canal was constructed through forced labor, the Spanish government compensated them 4 reals per month (*roughly equal to 44 pesos today*), and often, this meager amount never ended up in the laborer's hands.

In the 19th century, under Capitan Narciso Piramide, son of Capitan Venancio, the name of the barrio was changed for the third and final time, from Tamolayag to Padre Burgos. He chose the name to pay tribute to Padre Jose Burgos, a Filipino priest and martyr, who fought for and dedicated his life to the Filipinization of all parishes, enabling Filipino priests to manage and lead parishes and dioceses. In this century, the early Burgosanon faithful also encountered abuses from the religious friars. The local church was under the supervision of the mother church in Malitbog, overseen by the regular orders. Every time a mass was held in the local church, it became a daily strain for the early Burgosanons. An instance of these abuses, as narrated by the early Burgosanons, was that when a mass was set to be held in the barrio, the Spanish friar would refuse to celebrate it unless the congregation would carry him on a palanquin (*a portable, enclosed seat or bed, mounted on two bamboo poles and carried by people*) from Malitbog to Padre Burgos. It was a sorrowful experience for the spiritual life of the early Burgosanon believers who longed to embrace the joyful message of the Savior's love for humanity.

Because of the unfortunate experience and the desire for spiritual development and guidance of the early Burgosanon, Capitan Ciso, as he was lovingly called, along with the leaders and residents of the barrio, embraced the Filipino church established by Don Isabelo De Los Reyes, Sr., a senator and head of the Union Obrero Democratica, and led by Gregorio Aglipay Y Labayan, a former Roman Catholic priest appointed by President Emilio Aguinaldo as the Vicario-Heneral of the military and the church's first Supreme Bishop. The Filipino church, otherwise known as Iglesia Filipina Independiente (*Philippine Independent Church*), which, as stated by Dr. Teodoro Agoncillo, is "the only living and tangible result of the 1896 revolution", making the barrio take pride in having the church at its center. At the request of Capitan Ciso, Bishop Aglipay appointed Reverendo Padre Gorgonio Guerrero as the first pastor of the new barrio church, to guide the early Burgosanon faithful in their quest for spiritual direction and nourishment, and to freely administer the sacraments to the Christian community.

In the 20th century, the leaders of Padre Burgos started to work towards the political independence of the barrio. A dream of self-governance and self-determination from the discrimination of other neighboring barrios and municipalities. The aspiration for the political liberation of the barrio started in 1920. Reverend Father Arsenio Japson, an Aglipayan priest, traveled to Manila to seek a meeting with the late Congressman Tomas Oppus to propose a bill for transforming the barrio of Padre Burgos into a town. The next year, a three-member delegation was created to make further representation to the Leyte Provincial Board regarding the potential creation of Padre Burgos as a municipality. The three-person delegation consisted of Mr. Pedro Piramide Sr., a Vice-Mayor; Mr. Desiderio Orquez, a Municipal Councilor; and Atty. Santiago Palermo. The delegation, excluding Atty. Palermo traveled to Tacloban and met with Honorable Vicente De la Cruz, who was the Provincial Governor of Leyte at that time. The mission, nonetheless, failed due to the documents containing all the required municipal requisites, which were given to Atty. Palermo failed to arrive at the office of the Provincial Governor. The more disappointing news was that the documents were nowhere to be found.

With the unsuccessful attempt of the three-member delegation, the hope for political independence of the barrio faded when World War II began. Following the liberation of the Philippines by the Americans, Mr. Teodorico Esclamado and other distinguished Burgosanons established Saint James Academy (SJA), rekindling the call for Padre Burgos' independence in the spirit of every Burgosanon.

The much-awaited time came when Mr. Teodorico Esclamado became the Mayor of Malitbog on November 22, 1955. He prepared the requirements for making a new municipality. During his official trips to Manila to seek financial aid from the national government for the improvement of Malitbog, he also worked for the conversion of barrio Padre Burgos into a municipality. The sailing, though rough, difficult, and stormy, was successful. A delegation composed of Councilor Teodulo D. Ebuenga Sr., Barrio Lieutenant Jovencio Turcal, Mr. Pedro Piramide Sr., and Atty. Alejandro Esclamado sought an audience with President Carlos P. Garcia and succeeded in winning the President's favor to sign Executive Order No. 265, creating Padre Burgos a new Municipality. Upon the E.O. of the President, the Leyte Governor, Honorable Bernardo Torres, at exactly 5:00 A.M. on 22 October 1957, proclaimed Padre Burgos a new Municipality during the incumbency of Mayor Teodorico Esclamado Sr.

Presently, the Municipality of Padre Burgos has 11 barangay local government units, namely: Poblacion, Buenavista, Sta. Sofia, Tangkaan, Cantutang, Lungsodaan, Dinahugan, Sto. Rosario, Bunga, San Juan, and Laca.

Truly, the Municipality of Padre Burgos is a historical gem and one of the promising towns of the Province of Southern Leyte. It is blessed with scenic views, abundant aquamarine life and agricultural resources, a rich heritage of culture and arts (*considering that Padre Burgos is the birthplace of street-presentations in the Province of Southern Leyte, like the famous Tambula, a series of drama and musical presentations related to the story of the birth of Jesus Christ, and Los Tres Reyes, a reenactment of the journey of the three wise men*), growing enterprises, and a happy, resilient, persevering, competitive, and godly Burgosanons. Padre Burgos, today, has transformed into a vital link for people-to-people connectivity and commerce, acting as a maritime transport center that connects the islands of Visayas and Mindanao. This milestone manifests the potential and vitality of this humble town in its desire for an inclusive and sustainable local development.

